

Diagnostic System of Pressure Transformer Potentials

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Abstract:

The objective of the study is to study the diagnostic system of pressure transformers' problems. Based on a literature review and fact, the author has garbage the methods and analyzed the results of potential fault diagnosis systems of the pressure transformers in Vietnam

Keywords: Pressure transformers, potential problems

1. Introduction

A force transformer (PRESSURE TRANSFORMER) is a key device in the energy system. Their reliability not only affects the ability to supply electricity, but also affects the economic performance of a given consumer (e.g. smelters, production lines, etc. factory). For example, a fault of a distribution PRESSER could cause thousands of households to lose power. A fault of a surge transformer could cause power outages of adjacent areas in the grid system. That electricity.

Diagnosing potential problems of transducers in electrical system is a problem that has been concerned by many scientists. In order to be able to give information about possible future faults (faults) of a PRESSURE transducer, in a number of works, diagnostic methods based on the analysis of dissolved gas in oil. There are also diagnostic methods based on the PRESSURE TRANSFORMER's spectrum response, the diagnosis is based on the vibration of the PRESSURE transducer. Gas chromatography with oil-soluble gas analysis [1] requires specialized measuring equipment and requires high accuracy. Based on these techniques, there are many modern techniques that allow for better diagnosis [11], however one thing in common of these methods is that they must be based on precise measurement techniques. Therefore, the results of diagnosis also depend heavily on the accuracy of the measurements. Another diagnostic method that can inherit expert knowledge in the form of statistical law has been introduced [12], [16]. This method is developed based on the use of artificial neural networks. To get accurate diagnostic results, according to the method of using neural networks, it is necessary to have experimental data set "large enough" to train the network and choose a reasonable network structure. In fact, according to this approach, there are many network architectures that can be selected with different diagnostic results. Large network training time is also a drawback of this approach. In addition, methods using fuzzy logic, fuzzy-neural are also proposed [17], [18], [15]. The common point of these methods is to inherit expert knowledge on the basis of the law system.

In Vietnam, decision support systems based on artificial intelligence are developed on the basis of using expert knowledge such as expert system, neural network, logic fuzzy. also gradually developed widely. It can be seen that a number of studies have been published such as the application of fuzzy systems [2], neural networks [3], expert systems [4], or a combination of expert systems, neural networks and logic fuzzy to develop diagnostic systems. Diagnose potential transformer problems [5] [10]. The common point of these studies is the use of expert knowledge system. However, research to find new and more effective methods is always a requirement of the development process.

2. Literature review

2.1. Overview of pressure transformers

As we know electricity is the type of energy widely used in production and life, the electrification of industry, agriculture, transportation and other economic sectors requires different equipment. . The transmission of power from the power plant to the consumer requires a transmission line and a transformer station (a voltage-reducing

transformer station at the end of the line to match the voltage of the consumption load). From there it is clear that the VOLTAGE MACHINE is only responsible for changing voltage levels, or distributing energy, not converting energy.

Currently, our country's PRESSURE Transformer manufacturing industry has produced many different types of PRESSURE TRANSFORMERS, before putting the PRESSURE TRANSFORMER into operation must be tested for acceptance, to determine the quality of the flux transducer. through the specifications.

2.2. Basic parameters of the transformer

The ratings are given on the machines, other parameters listed by the manufacturer in the machine profile. Specific parameters are as follows.

a) Rated capacity

Is apparent power (total power) given from the secondary side of a PRESSURE MACHINE.

- Symbol: S_{dm}

- Unit of calculation: kVA (or VA).

b) Rated voltage

Rated primary voltage: is the voltage of the primary winding.

- Symbol: $U1_{dm}$

- Unit: kV (or V).

Rated secondary voltage: is the voltage of the secondary winding when the VOLTAGE IS OFF is idle and the voltage applied to the primary winding is rated.

- Symbol: $U2_{dm}$

- Unit: kV (or V).

For 3-coil PRESSURE transformers with UT_{dm} , UH_{dm} .

c) Primary and secondary rated currents:

These are the line currents of the primary and secondary winding corresponding to the rated power and voltage.

- Symbols: $I1_{dm}$, $I2_{dm}$

- Unit of calculation: (or A) For 1-phase transformer:

d) Rated frequency: Industrial frequency 50Hz

- Symbol: f_{dm} .

- Unit: Hz.

e) Short-circuit voltage of the VOLTAGE MACHINE

Is the voltage measured when short-circuiting one side of the coil such that the current reaches the rated value for a two-coil VOLTAGE Transformer, we have: U_c high-low.

- 3 values of short-circuit voltage with 3 coil pairs: High – Low; High-Middle; Middle - Lower.

- Short-circuit voltage in% ($U_k\%$).

f) No-load current I_0 (A)

The no-load current is the r.m.s.value of the current flowing through the coil, when the voltage applied to that winding is rated at the rated frequency and the other windings are left open, this current is also called magnetized stream.

g) No-load loss

The active power absorbed when no load is passed through the coil. This loss is also known as iron loss. Unit (kW), symbol P_0 .

h) Short-circuit loss

Is the active power absorbed in the winding of a VOLTAGE MACHINE when a load current passes through the coil. When a rated current passes through the poles of one of the windings, the poles of the other coil are short-circuited. If there are other windings, they are left open circuited (IEC.76.1).

- Symbol: P_n

- Unit: W (or kW).

i) Wiring team

Is the phase displacement angle of the primary and secondary wire voltages, there are 12 groups of wires, the coils can be connected to each other $\square$ or $\square$.

Transformer test

TESTING A PRESSURE MACHINE to determine component status and working of a PRESSURE MACHINE.

a) Overall external inspection

- Porcelain is not chipped.

- The seal does not detect oil, the anti-moisture seed does not change color.

- Good fan system, enough oil level.

- The details are installed as designed. The parameters of the PRESSURE MACHINE are in accordance with the document.

b) No load test

Purpose: to determine whether the coil and core have been shorted, displaced or the magnetic circuit is buckled, bolts are not squeezed, the core quality is bad. No load test is the first check item before Carry out the test of items to avoid residual magnetization in the magnetic circuit when the DC is charged The measured result is compared with the factory data or the value given on the machine mark If the measurement is not normal, we need to find a reason due to demagnetization and testing of the ratio of variables and measurements on DC resistors to conclude accurately.

c) Measurement of insulation resistance and winding absorption coefficient of the transformer

This is a criterion to evaluate the insulation status of the windings through the value of resistors R_{60} "and R_{15} ". The value of R_{60} "must be met with the voltage level for which it is operating. The required insulation resistance value depends on the manufacturer's specifications.

- With equipment used to measure insulation resistance using a 2500V or 5000V megohmmeter. The windings are short-circuited and grounded for at least 5 minutes to discharge all charge causing measurement errors.
- Measure the resistance of the windings between the windings, between the windings and the shell, and connect the shell to ground.

d) Measure the dc resistance of windings

Purpose:

- Determination of winding integrity, weld contact, joint, contact of the selector knife of the tap changer.
- Measurement is carried out on all high-voltage, medium-voltage and low-voltage windings and at the winding branches, in all phases.
- With PRESSURE TRANSFORMERS with switches we must measure at all steps.

The measurement results show whether the branch ends are correct or not.

e) Check the variable ratio

Purpose: To determine the number of winding turns of the winding at all tapping. Combined with other indicators to determine short-loop. Determine the high voltage and low voltage winding.

f) Check the wiring

Wiring is the phase difference angle between the line voltage (or phase voltage) of the high-voltage side winding compared to the line voltage (phase voltage) of the low-voltage side winding of the same name.

Symbol:

- The end of the ABC high voltage line is XYZ.
- The end of the low voltage line abc is xyz.

The wiring group of a PRESSURE MACHINE is one of the conditions of parallel operation of a PRESSURE MACHINE. To determine whether the wiring group is correct with the symbol written on the machine mark or not, we can use the specialized equipment TETTEX-2793 to measure or use the 3-digit DC pulse method. The basis for the correct connection of the PRESSURE MACHINE protection profile.

g) Test of insulating oil

The job of the oil in a PRESSURE TRANSFER is to insulate and cool. Testing of transformer oil: in order to ensure safe operation of the VOLTAGE MACHINE, we must check the quality of the oil through the items. Measure disruptive discharge voltage, measure dielectric loss angle at 90oC.

Above is the introduction of a number of experiments to determine basic parameters, in addition to some tests to determine other parameters such as:

- Measure insulation resistance and output ceramic dielectric loss of a PRESSURE TRANSFORMER with oil-paper insulation.
- Measure the dielectric loss angle that reflects the insulation qualities of windings.
- Test of built-in current transformers in PRESSURE transformers.
- Check the transformer regulator loop graph.
- Test of alternating voltage at high industrial frequencies.

2.3. Potential error diagnosis methods

A major concern about potential failures of a pressure transducer is deterioration of the insulation system. This can lead to the problem of whether the insulation system will be disrupted by current pulses (electrodynamic forces on the coil) or overvoltage. Diagnosis of potential transformer error is associated with the assessment of the insulation conditions of the insulating materials in the PRESSER. The assessment can be done directly by testing or by indirect evaluation through different methods.

Check and evaluate the insulation condition

Insulation test evaluation mainly refers to periodic off-line tests, including insulation resistance (IR) measurement, dielectric loss coefficient (DLF), polarization surface (IP) uses abnormal IR and the dispersion frequency of capacitance, rotation factor (TP), coil resistance, ground rod resistance (CGR) and some other checks. The above tests are applicable to the entire PRESSURE TRANSFORMER and it is the main measurement under the insulation condition. They may indicate some PRESSERATOR condition problems but may not find potential errors. Other checks for insulation paper or paperboard samples are taken from a PRESSER. The above tests include measurements of polymerization (DP) and tension (TS). A number of relevant new methods such as color analysis of insulating oils, ISP surface polarization spectroscopy using voltage feedback (RV) and analytical techniques are also used with the same purpose. Inspection techniques that have to interfere with the inside of a PRESSER are unfavorable because sampling can jeopardize the integrity of the insulation system, but may also be necessary with PRESSURE TRANSFORMER is too old.

The best test methods for assessing the insulation of a pressure transducer are on-line forms, including partial discharge monitoring and partial discharge analysis. soluble gas. These online tests are also key methods in diagnosing potential errors.

Online partial discharge monitoring - PD

PD is produced by fault conditions related to moisture, voids in solid insulators, metal particles and air bubbles. It can even cause damage to the dielectric. A significant increase in PD level and in the coefficient of increase in PD activity can give an early indication of a potential defect.

Online PD monitoring methods usually fall into two forms: electric method and negative method. As far as the use of the sensor is used, both types are categorized into two smaller types: non-intrusion monitoring and intrusion monitoring (intrusion here refers to interference inside a VOLTAGE MACHINE). Non-intrusive monitoring uses sensors mounted on the outside of a VOLTAGE MACHINE such as condenser, high frequency current transformers, pressure type accelerometer, etc.

Penetration conditions must place the PD sensors in the PRESSURE TRANSFORMER so this interference would endanger the parts of the PRESSURE MACHINE and be more costly. For safety reasons, fiber sensors are more commonly used than other types of sensors when for intrusive type PD monitoring.

In electrical PD monitoring, the PD pulse current is usually measured directly through a capacitive circuit or a high frequency current transformer (HFCT). The coupling capacitors can be a PD-free high voltage decoupling capacitor placed next to the output load of a PRESSURE Transformer or the use of bushings directly. The main problem with electrical PD monitoring is interference. Solving this can involve very complex algorithms and may not always be resolved in practical applications.

Negative PD supervision has been focusing research in both academic and practical fields in industry over the years. The driving force for this research direction is the benefit that can be obtained through locally precision PDs. There have been many theoretical studies on local PD principles and a number of systems have been developed for this purpose. The applications have shown that there are still causes that make it difficult to interpret the results, and they require more meaningful research.

For example, the negative velocity is influenced by many factors, including the temperature of the oil, gas and water contained in the oil, and the carrier frequency of the negative signal. Using a constant value in the problem of a local PD function can give very sketchy results. A major problem with PD monitoring is results. At present, there are no general rules that can correlate the transformer state with the activities of the PD or even a clear classification of PD activities is not available. Using only one parameter is an empirical PD-level limit value. It seems acceptable for this value as it is not indicated in any state standards.

Analysis of dissolved gas in oil (DGA)

A more successful technique for diagnosing potential errors online is oil gas solubility analysis. Oil-soluble analysis of a PRESSURE MACHINE is aimed at early detection of local overheating, low level discharges. The development of these processes will lead to malfunction. Development failures during this period were not detected by the throttle relay. Small amounts of gases are formed continuously through small decomposition in oil or in hard insulation. To analyze dissolved gas in oil, a Transformer Oil Gas Analysis System uses an analyzer system called TOGAS (Transformer Oil Gas Analysis System). From the analysis of the dissolved gas in the oil of the PRESSURE MACHINE, we can diagnose the failure types of the PRESSURE MACHINE (according to IEC 599). DGA analysis when there is no need to disconnect the power of a VOLTAGE MACHINE, also known as "online" or online method. This type of analysis includes the conventional DGA, which is based on periodic oil sampling and the modern technique of on-line gas monitoring.

Conventional DGA has been implemented for a number of years and has achieved tremendous success compared with other techniques. The main reason for this success is that the sampling and sample analysis process is simple and inexpensive, and easy to standardize. Numerous experiments have been carried out from this process and many DGA standards have been established: IEC 599, IEC 599R, C57.104, etc. The main standardized gases have been identified as hydrogen (H_2), methane (CH_4), ethane (C_2H_6), ethylene (C_2H_4), acetylene (C_2H_2), CO and CO_2 .

One important issue with conventional DGA methods, however, is the reliability of the results. As the PRESSURE transformers differ in size, structure, manufacturer, load mode and maintenance history can also have distinct gas characteristics, they need to be considered separately in most cases. So the DGA is often seen as "experience", not science.

Online oil gas monitoring appeared soon after the DGA technique was announced. A lot of early research and commercial products were also published. Some monitors focus on H_2 only while others focus on many other gases as well. One benefit of online monitoring is the continuous measurement of one or more gases so any information needed for potential failure monitoring can be easily obtained.

Issues related to these monitors are the choice and durability of the gas element filters, the measuring range and the insulation properties. Selectivity is shown in filtering skills that allow certain gases to pass through and block the remaining gases. Poor selection will result in lower measurement accuracy. The unstable filters will deteriorate more quickly, especially under highly variable temperature working conditions such as mid-summer and winter, even mid-day and night. The information at the monitoring points were non-electrical quantities, while the measuring device readings contained electrical circuits. These circuits are essentially converter circuits and often have a linear or nonlinear conversion characteristic. The accuracy of the meter depends on the temperature, humidity, of the working environment.

In general, the measuring range and insulation capacity of online monitoring equipment sometimes deviate from the experimental tests by other methods. With the new generation of monitors, this gap is closing. For all reasons, the online monitor is used as a testing tool to initially identify possible anomalies. The detailed error diagnosis was then switched to the conventional DGA.

3. Research method

- Find out about the common faults of the pressure transducer while operating in the electrical system. Research on diagnostic process, theoretical basis and diagnostic methods. Find out the research results that have been published in the country and abroad on the diagnosis of the PRESSURE TRANSFORMER fault previously. In particular, learn about the diagnostic method of PRESSURE TRANSFORMER based on the analysis of dissolved gas (DGA - Dissolved Gas Analysis). Evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of the method. Proposing a new model for the diagnostic system according to the approximation approach. Discuss with experts in electrical testing.

- Install the software based on the designed algorithm; Tested on real data and calibrated software.

4. Result

Diagnosis of potential transformer error on DGA basis

Gas-producing properties

Oil-soluble analysis of a PRESSURE MACHINE is aimed at early detection of local overheating, low level discharges etc. To analyze dissolved gas in oil, a Transformer Oil Gas Analysis System uses an analyzer system called TOGAS (Transformer Oil Gas Analysis System). From the results of the analysis of the dissolved gas in the oil of the PRESSURE MACHINE, we can diagnose the failure types of the PRESSURE MACHINE. DGA analysis when there is no need to disconnect the power of a VOLTAGE MACHINE, also known as "online" or online method. This type of analysis includes the conventional DGA, which is based on periodic oil sampling and the modern technique of on-line gas monitoring.

Under the action of electricity and heat, the hydrogen – carbon ($H-C$) particles of oil minerals can be decomposed into hydrogen and $H-C$ fragments, which can combine to create gases. are hydrohen (H_2), methane (CH_4), ethane (C_2H_6), ethylene (C_2H_4), acetylene (C_2H_2), CO and CO_2 . The amount of gas for each individual gas depends on the temperature in the vicinity of the point of impact. Many researchers have proposed different methods to predict potential faults in a PRESSURE transformers such as Dornenberg's ratio, Roger ratio, main gas method, IEC-599 standard.

Potential errors of the PRESSER MACHINE

Potential faults of a pressure transducer can be classified into the following main categories: electric arcs, electric halo or partial discharge, cellulose overheating, oil overheating. The energy levels caused by these events are in order from high to low as follows: arc $\square$ overheating halo.

Table 1. Definition code of modified Rogers ratio method

Rate	Value	Code
CH ₄ /H ₂ (R1)	≤ 0.1	5
	0.1 – 1.0	0
	1 – 3	1
	≥ 3	2
C ₂ H ₆ /CH ₄ (R4)	< 1	0
	≥ 1	1
C ₂ H ₄ /C ₂ H ₆ (R5)	< 1	0
	1 – 3	1
	≥ 3	2
C ₂ H ₂ /C ₂ H ₄ (R2)	< 0.5	0
	0.5 – 3	1
	≥ 3	2

5. Conclusion

Diagnosing the potential breakdown of the pressure transducer in the electrical system is a problem that has been concerned by many scientists. In order to be able to give information about potential future faults of a PRESSURE transducer, in a number of projects, diagnostic methods based on oil dissolved gas analysis (DGA - Dissolved Gas in oil Analysis). There are also diagnostic methods based on the PRESSURE TRANSFORMER's spectrum response, the diagnosis is based on the vibration of the PRESSURE transducer. Gas chromatography with oil-0 gas-soluble analysis requires specialized measuring equipment and requires high accuracy. Based on these techniques, there are many modern techniques that allow better diagnosis than 0, however one common point of these methods is that it must be based on precise measurement techniques. Therefore, the results of diagnosis also depend much on the accuracy of the measurements. Another diagnostic method that can inherit expert knowledge in the form of statistical law has been introduced 0, 0. This method is developed based on the use of artificial neural networks. To get accurate diagnostic results, according to the method of using neural networks, it is necessary to have experimental data set "large enough" to train the network and choose a reasonable network structure. In fact, according to this approach, there are many network architectures that can be selected with different diagnostic results. Large network training time is also a drawback of this approach. In addition, the methods using fuzzy logic, fuzzy-neural are also proposed 0, 0, 0. The common point of these methods is inheriting expert knowledge. In Vietnam, decision support systems based on artificial intelligence are developed on the basis of using expert knowledge such as expert system, neural network, fuzzy logic, etc. is also gradually developed widely. Some studies on building fault diagnosis systems for transducers have been published, such as the application of fuzzy 0 system, neural network 0, expert system 0, or a combination of expert systems, neural networks and logic fuzzy. to develop a diagnostic system for potential fault transformers 0 - 0. However, research to find new and more efficient methods is always necessary in the scientific and technological development process.

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